

STEALTH AIRFRAME DESIGN METHODOLOGY FOR HIGH ALTITUDE REAL-TIME RECONNAISSANCE DRONES

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SUMMARY: This paper presents the design philosophy behind the development of a Stealth Unmanned Air Vehicle (UAV) for real-time reconnaissance applications. The aspects of the threat analysis, the mission analysis and the Radar Cross Section (RCS) requirement definition leading to the design concept of the airframe, are introduced. The Electro Magnetic (EM) design requirements for low radar signature are derived and brought into context with the development of the composite airframe.

The stealth design methodology of the radar absorbing composite structure is illustrated on the inward slanted dorsal fin of the specific UAV. The paper addresses the use of analytical modelling techniques for low RCS geometric shaping and presents a detailed design of the fin employing the electro-magnetically tuned composite materials. The special tooling and manufacturing processes of the stealthy fin are discussed. The work is concluded with a summary of the results of the electro-magnetic tests, the environmental tests and the structural qualification of the dorsal fin hardware.

KEYWORDS: stealth airframe design methodology, radar absorbing composite structures, radar cross section reduction, dorsal fin design and development

INTRODUCTION

Designing a composite airframe structure is as technically challenging as it is complex by nature. However, by taking this composite structure, and introducing the requirements for a low radar cross section signature airframe, a new dimension of complexity is added in terms of the design, materials, manufacturing and processing techniques.

The airframe geometry, its structure and the internal layout, is dictated by the system requirement specifications. For an airframe with a low radar cross section signature, these are not only defined through the design guidelines for aerodynamic, structural and material inputs, but also by the requirement for a specific electro-magnetic performance.

The materials required for the airframe structure, conventionally defined to perform to certain mechanical characteristics, now need to be defined by their electro-magnetic performance, ie the properties of permeability and the transmissivity. A whole new design methodology needs to be established which takes into consideration the aspects of geometric shaping, structural optimization and the application of electro-magnetically tuned composite materials.

The inward slanted dorsal fin of the Flowchart 2 Stealth technology demonstrator, an Unmanned Air Vehicle (UAV) for use as a high altitude real-time reconnaissance drone, is used in this case study to demonstrate the various aspects of low observability design. Refer to Fig.1.

Fig 1: Flowchart 2 Stealth Technology Demonstrator

STEALTH REQUIREMENT ANALYSIS

A brief introduction into the field of stealth technology is presented, to illustrate how the design of an airframe is driven by the system requirement for low observability. The chronological steps involved in the stealth requirement analysis [1] are discussed below. Refer to Fig. 2.

Threat Analysis

In the threat analysis the target scenario that is to be encountered, is established. This entails the identification of the different threat radars and air defence systems, such as Surface to Air Missile systems (SAM's) and Anti Aircraft (AA) gun systems, which are employed at the target area. The different threats are then characterized and prioritized in terms of their potential influence on the mission effectiveness.

Mission Analysis

In the mission analysis the primary mission is specified and the type of system required to conduct this mission is selected. The system requirement specifications define the type of airframe and provide inputs to the airframe performance. The mission profile is then defined to ensure maximum mission effectiveness.

Radar Cross Section Requirement Definition

The RCS requirement definition establishes the maximum allowable RCS for the airframe, to ensure that the primary mission is conducted successfully with a high degree of survivability. From the threat scenario and the planned mission profile, the radar illumination angles during the mission are calculated. The type of electro-magnetic scattering mechanisms and the expected radar return, ie the RCS of the airframe, are analysed with the use of analytical methods. The data is then used to define the basic geometric shape of the airframe. [2]

Survivability Study

The survivability study forms part of the strategic analysis. Analytical modelling techniques are employed to determine the threat performances, such as radar detection ranges, kinematic ranges, system accuracies, flight profiles and time over target, etc. Based on this the probability of detection [3] and ultimately the survivability and mission effectiveness of the airframe is established.

Fig 2: Stealth Requirement Analysis

AIRFRAME DESIGN

The system requirement specifications for the Flowchart 2 high altitude real-time reconnaissance drone are presented. The design methodology for low RCS signature is then illustrated in a case study on the UAV's inward slanted dorsal fin.

System Requirement Specifications

The system requirement specification for the UAV dictate high subsonic speeds at an altitude of 40 000 ft during its ingress and egress phase. It descends to the reconnaissance level while maintaining the high subsonic speed throughout the reconnaissance phase. The airframe is designed to a sustained load factor of +5g and -3g with a maximum instantaneous load factor of +8g. The UAV falls in the 1 000 kg class and with an unspecified payload capability it has an approximate flight time of 60 minutes.

The airframe is ground launched with the use of two discardable solid rocket boosters, accelerating the airframe at 10g during the launch phase. Recovery is induced through the use of a drag and a main parachute. Inflatable landing bags are used to absorb the landing loads, which are limited to 15g. Emphasis is placed on the requirement for an all composite airframe structure, which is easily containerized in standard ISO containers to ensure ease of transportability and rapid deployment.

From the stealth requirement analysis the main threat radars in this potential threat scenario have been identified as mono-static radar systems, operating in the C- and X-band. With the primary mission being reconnaissance, a high - low - high flight profile is required. For this flight profile, the biggest threat of detection occurs when the UAV is in its final sector of the ingress phase. Under this condition the airframe is primarily subjected to radar illumination angles in the forward sector defined by -5° to $+15^{\circ}$ in elevation and $\pm 35^{\circ}$ in azimuth.

To ensure a probability of detection of less than 90% during the final ingress phase, the RCS requirement definition implies that the maximum RCS of the airframe must not exceed -10 dBsm (fictitious value) in the direction of the threat radars transmitter/receiver. Although the design is optimized for mono-static radar systems, the maximum RCS from any aspect angle should not exceed -12 dBsm (fictitious value). This system requirement is applicable for the full frequency range in the C and X band, for both planar and circular polarized radar systems.

Detail Design: Case Study Dorsal Fin

The system requirement specifications dictate a range of design constraints on the dorsal fin. [4] These are summarized:

- i) aerodynamic design, defined by factors such as the aircraft flight envelope, manoeuvrability, drag, aerodynamic efficiency, etc.
- ii) structural design, defined by the aerodynamic and inertia loads, and the combination of aerodynamic and structural interaction, the aero-elastic behaviour.
- iii) electro-magnetic design, defined by the requirements for low observability through geometric shaping and the application of electro-magnetically tuned composite materials.

- iv) materials, the composite materials have to provide certain mechanical properties to ensure structural integrity, as well as electro-magnetic properties to ensure the low RCS signature.

To achieve the system requirement specifications and satisfy the aerodynamic, structural, electro-magnetic design constraints, an iterative approach had to be taken to derive at the optimal fin structure.

Aerodynamic

A 65A008 NACA profile was selected for the dorsal fin to ensure optimal aerodynamic efficiency during high altitude high subsonic flight conditions. The leading edge was swept back through 25° and the trailing edge through 15° . The root chord was 400 mm and the fin 600 mm long. The fin loading was based on FAR 26, whereby the worst case aerodynamic load condition occurred at $Cl = 0.6$ (a side slip angle of 15° at VA), where VA was 300 knots. The resulting design load at these conditions was 2 000 N.

Structural

The structural design of the fin was based on ultimate load at 150% and yield at 120% of the design load of 2 000 N. In the load analysis an elliptical load distribution along the centre chord was used. A preliminary structural design was conducted to establish the skin construction and fibre lay-up. The basic dimensions of the 20% and 60% spars were established and the concept for the finbox at the fin/wing intersection was defined. Maximum fin deflection and flutter was investigated.

Electro-magnetic

At the C- and X-band frequencies the electro-magnetic wavelengths are far shorter than the length of the airframe, implying that the design is driven by high frequency scattering mechanisms. For this high frequency scattering mechanism, the effects of detail geometric shaping and the use of electro-magnetic material parameters become critical. (For resonant and/or Rayleigh type scattering regimes, this would be less applicable). [5]

A software code, based on Physical Optics (PO), was developed to establish the backscattered field for a conductive constant chord reference fin. The code was then hybridized with the Geometrical Theory of Diffraction (GTD) code, to enable further evaluation of the fields of diffraction. The analytical model was subsequently upgraded to include the effects of the different electro-magnetically tuned composite material parameters. From this analytical model the main contributors to the RCS and their relative contributions were established.

The model was then upgraded to enable the RCS prediction of the fin within the surroundings of the fuselage and the main wing. Given the system/fin boundary conditions, the electro-magnetic scattering mechanisms could be established. The highest contribution to the RCS was due to a combination of reflection and diffraction along the fin leading and trailing edge, with surface wave energy propagating along the skin surface. The interference reflection between the fin and the fuselage formed a large contribution to the RCS of the airframe.

The plan shape of the fin was subsequently optimized. The sweepback angle of the fin leading edge was increased, the fin tip was smoothed and a radius along the root of the fin base was added. To reduce the high reflection/diffraction off the fin leading edge, a low impedance RAM was selected in this area. To reduce the surface wave energy along the skins, and due to a limitation in skin thicknesses, a high impedance RAM was employed along the skins. The material construction was that of an outer dielectric skin (Epoxy/glass fibre), a Nomex RAM core and an inner dielectric skin (Epoxy/glass fibre). The skin thicknesses had to be impedance matched and it was critical to the optimal performance of the RAM that the dielectric skins did not vary in thickness.

To prevent direct illumination of the inner mechanics of the fin, ie the main spars, the electrical connections, the control rods, etc, this area was covered with a conductive inner skin. This inner skin formed part of the wing torsion box, whereby the skin was made of Epoxy/carbon fibre to the correct fibre lay up, satisfying the bending and torsional stiffness requirements. The shape of this inner skin was critical to achieve a low RCS, and had to be optimized for minimal radar return for the main threat illumination angles. For details of the design concept of the dorsal fin cross section, refer to Fig. 3.

The carbon spars were bonded to the inner conductive skin and continued into the fin root box, to transfer the fin loads to the airframe bulkheads. Details such as control panels and the control surface interface increase the complexity of the stealthy fin design considerably. The discussion of these aspects have not been included in this paper.

Fig 3: Dorsal Fin Stealth Design

MANUFACTURE AND PROCESSING

The additional tooling and the complexity in the manufacturing processes for the construction of the stealthy fin, is discussed. The problems associated with the different RAM, the storage, handling and the environmental threats etc, are briefly mentioned.

Tooling

The basic tooling for the fin resembled that of conventional composite material tooling. The fin pattern was CNC machined from a type 65 aluminium block. A carbon composite mould, cured at a temperature of 60° C, was taken off the aluminium pattern and postcured at 120° C. The mould was subsequently stiffened with a carbon backing structure. Additional aluminium tooling had to be machined for the forming of a silicon insert which was required for shaping the inner conductive leading edge skin. Tooling was also required for the manufacture and positioning of the main spars.

Manufacture

The complexity in the manufacture of the fin was brought about by the fact that the different layers of composite materials, ie, the outer dielectric skin, the RAM core and the inner dielectric skin, were not allowed to vary in thickness by more than 5% over the total surface area. To maintain the transmissivity of these dielectric materials, the fibre matrix ratio's were not allowed to vary by more than 5%, as this again was critical to the optimal impedance matching of the RAM structure.

The leading edge RAM was CNC machined and bonded into position. The Nomex RAM was pre-cut and formed part of the skin lay-up procedure. Extreme care had to be taken during the integration of the RAM, that no air was allowed to be trapped in the construction and no resin was allowed to migrate towards the RAM core. This had to be achieved while at the same time maintaining good bonding between the surfaces to ensure the required structural integrity.

Material Handling

The environmental and health hazards associated with some of the RAM formed a major problem. Special storage facilities were required, whereby protection against contamination of the raw materials was ensured. The facilities had to ensure good environmental control, as some of the materials only had a limited shelf life. The high toxicity and the combustibility of some materials, made it paramount to ensure strict safety regulations. Special handling methods needed to be implemented, and the personnel had to wear protective clothing due to the health hazards associated with some of the RAM.

TEST RESULTS

The dorsal fin was subjected to extensive environmental, static and dynamic structural tests and electro-magnetic performance measurements. The electro-magnetic evaluation of the radar absorbing materials in the free space measurement facility, for the qualification of the materials, is not discussed in this paper. [6] & [7]

Structural Testing

The structural tests were conducted in the Structural Research and Test Laboratory at Kentron. The tests were grouped into static and dynamic load cases. In the static load case, the fin was initially subjected to yield loading at 120% of the design load, and subsequently to ultimate loading at 150% of the design load. In the dynamic load case, the fin was subjected to twice the fatigue life cycle spectrum of the airframe. [8]

The full set of structural tests were repeated after completion of the environmental tests, to establish whether the environmental testing had any negative effects on the structural integrity of the fin. [9]

Environmental Testing

The environmental tests were conducted to establish the effects of the different environmental conditions on the structural integrity and the electro-magnetic performance of the RAM. These tests included Ultra Violet (UV) tests, fungal growth, humidity and temperature cycling. Furthermore the structure was subjected to aircraft fuels, low viscosity lubricating oils and cleaning agents for extended periods of time. [9]

Electro-magnetic Testing

The electro-magnetic tests were conducted in a radar test facility representing far field conditions, to establish the design efficiency in terms of the RCS signature. One fin, coated with a conductive outer skin, was tested to establish a baseline and to determine the geometric constraints. The tests were then repeated with the stealthy fin, which incorporated the different radar absorbing materials. [8]

The electro-magnetic tests for the stealthy fin were repeated after the fin was subjected to the environmental tests, to establish whether the electro-magnetic testing had any deteriorating effects on the electro-magnetic performance of the fin. [9]

CONCLUSION

To optimize the design of low observable composite aircraft structures, the system requirements for aerodynamic design, structural design and electro-magnetic design have to be optimally harmonized. Furthermore, from a materials aspect, the use of advanced composite materials, in combination with electro-magnetically tuned materials, require the development of completely new design, manufacturing and processing techniques.

A design methodology was established for the design of stealthy composite material airframe structures. This was illustrated by a case study on the inward slanted dorsal fin of the Flowchart 2 high speed reconnaissance drone. It was successfully demonstrated that the RCS requirement specifications were achieved and that the associated technologies are well established. For the UAV and associated airframe components, such as engine intakes, wings, canards, etc, the above design methodology can now be applied.

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